

Towards Utilizing Hands-held Mobile Devices in Post COVID-19 for Curriculum Delivery in Tertiary Institution of Learning in Nigeria

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Abstract

Globally, Teaching and Learning Process in Tertiary Institutions of learning is gradually been overtaken with the used of some forms of technology or the other, this is so because the traditional ways and medium of instructional process in tertiary institutions of learning which is perpetually still in usage is not yielding much desire results in terms of learning outcomes for students and teachers, especially in this post-covid period. Based on the foregoing, this paper examined some hand-held mobile devices that can be used towards reducing crisis in curriculum delivery in tertiary institutions of learning-in Nigeria. Therefore, two major categorizations of hand-held mobile devices that can be use in tertiary institutions for ease of curriculum delivery are: Personal digital assistants (PDA), tablet PCs and portable media players, these types of devices increasingly used a touch screen interface; While in the second categorizations are: Cellphone; iPad.; iPod; Blackberry; PDA & Handheld Computers. which can improve productivity by making information accessible on the go; Portables handheld devices usually have a lower specification and run slower; Significantly, it improves the speed of service and take the user experience to the next level. Finally, the paper highlighted some challenges such as: Portability which could lead to lost or stolen of device; keyboards are smaller than those of laptop etc. Thereafter, the paper concludes with suggesting & recommendations towards the use of hand-held device to reduced existing crisis in curriculum delivery, such as improve infrastructure deficit, students overcrowding in classroom and of course allow for co-operative learning and individual-pace learning amongst other

Keywords: Hands-held mobile devices, Tertiary Institution, Crisis & Curriculum

Introduction

Coronavirus diseases of 2019 (COVID-19) is a menace that has bedeviled and ravaged the world in many ways. It has retarded the economy, ravaged health system, destroyed hospitality business, and disrupted socio-political interaction and now, inducing an unannounced shift away from the traditional classroom settings in the educational sector to the used of modern technologies in curriculum delivery. This is sequel to the rising concerns about the spread

of COVID-19 and the need to contain the virus, a growing number of tertiary institutions have shut down in regards to conventional classroom delivery. This is courtesy of the fact that a major strategy in the containment of coronavirus was through imposition of lockdowns which automatically retrained people from partaking in social activities. This situation has particularly been of a great challenge to the education system across the world. Globally, educational sector has never

witnessed such disruption in a colossal manner before. COVID-19 posed serious consequences for students by depriving them of their fundamental rights to education and exposing them to risk of child labour, early marriage, exploitation, and poor academic abilities. As attested by United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), more than 1.5 billion students globally which represents 87% of the global student population, were deprived of education. More worrisome is the threat of extended closures which paved way for the need to rethink traditional teaching ((Ali, 2020; Baytiyeh, 2018; UNESCO, 2020a; UNESCO, 2020b).

Therefore, with the rapid growth in Information Communication and Technologies (ICT) which have brought remarkable changes in the twenty-first century, as well as affected the demands of modern societies. ICT is becoming increasingly important in our daily lives and in our educational system. Hence, there is a growing demand on educational institutions to use ICT to teach the skills and knowledge students need for the 21st century. Realizing the effect of ICT on the workplace and everyday life, today's educational institutions are expected to restructure their educational curricula and classroom facilities, in order to bridge the existing technology gap in teaching and learning especially in this post covid-period. This restructuring process requires effective adoption of technologies into existing environment in order to provide learners with knowledge of specific subject t areas, to promote meaningful learning and to enhance professional productivity (Tomei, 2015)

Handheld mobile devices are forms of Information Communication and Technologies devices which primarily designed to provide a suite of computing, communication and informational tools in a

device about the size of standard palm. Typically, handheld devices are not as powerful as a computer, but modern handheld mobile devices increasingly include powerful dual-core processors, RAM, SD storage capacity, an operating system, and native and add-on applications. These are often powered by a dry cell lithium or similar battery. Moreover, these types of hand-held devices increasingly use a touch screen interface. Personal digital assistants (PDA), tablet PCs and portable media players are all considered handheld mobile devices. In the last few decades, the traditional teaching and learning activities have undergone so many changes. The existing of electronic education in institutions of learning in the 21st Century brought about rapid development and changes in all fields of human endeavour which is now being accepting, and spreading gradually worldwide. This is made possible largely by the emergence and rapid development worldwide in information and communications technology (ICT). The Global Network will enable easy access of information multimedia and artificial intelligence, enabling learners to gain access to more knowledge and to a variety of electronic educational media tools. Digital tools allow the most difficult tasks to become seamlessly easy and more efficient. In education, hand-held mobile devices allowed the dissemination of knowledge to be dispersed instantly and it allows for quicker and more effective communication. Also, allow students to be engaged and learn in ways that they never have in a setting before. Therefore, these hand-held mobile devices are portable device that can be carried and held in one's palm, a computing or electronic device that is compact and portable enough to be held and used in one or both hands such as cellular communication and other computing devices as thus. Cellphone; iPad.; iPod;

Blackberry; PDA.; Handheld Computers (Douglas. B, & David, S. 2012, Ndagi, 2015; Vaughan-Nichols, 2010).

Curriculum contents for Tertiary Educational System in Nigeria has been the same for almost twenty five years back and this is so because no Nigeria University cannot on its own develop or introduce a new course or program even if in high demand in the society and labour market without getting approval from the National University Commission (NUC) a regulating body of tertiary education provision in the country. Therefore, prescriptions of courses to run as regards faculties and departmental core-course and elective within a given areas of specialization in public universities in Nigeria must be ascertain and approved by the commission. But in the recent time it was made known that the federal government through the commission set to release a new curriculum for universities in the country, that seventeen additional disciplines would be introduce are currently being worked upon in diverse disciplines by a team of experts which is hoped to be rated one of the best in the world and which would ensuring that the academic programme of the nigeria university system become more globally competitive. That, these current curriculum contents would be easily deployed with the use of modern technological handheld devices such as personal digital assistance, (PDA), and relevant smarter handheld technologies compatible with course delivery of a given programme (Chila, 2022 & Tunboson, 2022)

In the tertiary institution of learning in Nigeria, and before the recent digitalization of instructional process in this 21st century, decades' back teaching and learning process have been provided in the traditional perspectives which characterized presence of teachers and students with the confinement of the classroom (face-to-face).

Gradually, with passage of time, a blended approach was introduced with used of some technological devices for students-teachers' interaction meant for instructional strategies. Currently, utilizing devices is becoming a norm and enshrined in the Nigeria educational policy. There are several learning theories that emphasized and support the use of hands-held devices in supporting instructional process in Nigeria university. Some of the relevant and backing theories hinged on constructivist theory and constructivism, experiential learning with the use of hand-held devices. The theory considered most relevantly the interaction of students/teachers' relationship in learning to be supported with digital devices and which uphold to learning based on individual pace & direct contact with an ideal tool to facilitates what needs to be learnt Therefore, Connectivism was championed by George Siemens (2015). It can be understood as educational theory or view or global strategy. (Armatas, Spratt & Vincent, 2013).' According to Siemens (2010), Constructivism, is a learning theory that takes into account changes in learning due to technology, not included in most common theories such as behaviorism, cognitivism, but constructivist theory considers increase of information, knowledge, and its sources in the digital age. (Spratt & Vincent, 2013).

The relevant of Connectivism theory to digital tools seen in its concept is based on the idea that Internet technologies have created new opportunities for students to learn and share information across networks, where learners develop knowledge through peer networks and online, and these connections are more important with the use of hand-held devices. The communication tools of handheld devices, coupled with the resources available through Internet connectivity it will help provides the scaffolding for connectivist learning and

provide the channels for interacting with dynamic sources of data. From a connectivist perspective, the process of going through a mobile learning experience is more important than any content that may happen to be learned in the process. Connectivism learning theories emphasized the use of technology with capability of (storing, supplying and manipulating information) and making connections, as well as creating useful information patterns. Connectivism views learning as building and using a network connectivity of hand-held devices. (Siemens, 2010; Ozan & Kesim, 2013).

Impact of Covid-19 on teaching and learning methodologies

Nigeria have experienced couple of lockdowns during the Covid-19 pandemic ranging from total to partial. These lockdown and social distancing affected all sector including the education sector. In fact, the government of the federation on realizing the extent of damage which this pandemic would cause and have caused in other countries, decided the lockdown of tertiary institution, which in its entirety affected teaching and learning. According to UNESCO (2020), what has had the most immediate impact has obviously been the temporary suspension of classroom activity which has left students, particularly undergraduates and those finishing high school and aspiring to begin tertiary education, in a completely new situation without a clear idea of how long the impact will last, and feeling its immediate effect on their daily life, cost of living and other financial burdens and, naturally, on the continuation of their studies. The mode of teaching in Nigerian tertiary institution as noted by Ifijeh and Yusuf (2020) has been the traditional method, which consists of lecturers or teachers having physical meetings with students in a classroom building for the purposes of lecture, examinations, seminars and project/thesis

defense, very few Nigerian universities operate e-learning platforms, which merely allowed for upload and download of lecture notes, as well as giving and submission of students' assignments. (Ifijeh et al. 2015).

The consequential impacts of Covid seems to consolidated on the earlier status of Nigeria tertiary education system which has been in shambles ranging from the constant loggerheads between the federal government and tertiary institution unions especially Academic Staff of Nigerian Universities (ASUU), decrease in the budget meant for education and poor infrastructures. Now that the pandemic has occurred, its effect had worsen the situation of tertiary education in Nigeria. According to Ogunode et al (2020), the after effect of COVID-19 to the tertiary education ranges from disruption of academic calendar, cancelation of already planned local and international conferences, teaching and learning gap, loss of workforce in educational institutions and cut in budget of higher education. Simon and Hans (2020) submitted that the global lockdown of education institutions has caused major (and likely unequal) interruption in students' learning; disruptions in internal assessments; and the cancellation of public assessments for qualifications or their replacement by an inferior alternative. Ogunode (2020) observed that the closure of all educational institutions from primary schools to the higher institutions affected the students' academic plans and programme because many of the higher institutions have started their first semester exams. (Ogunode; 2020).

It was a reiterated fact that, education as we all know is a key to a nation's development and Nigeria as a country is not an exemption. At the tertiary level of education, the system consists of a university sector and a non-university sector. The latter is composed of polytechnics and colleges of education. The tertiary sector as a whole

offers opportunity for undergraduate, graduate, and vocational and technical education. The National Policy on Education (FGN, 2013), defines tertiary education as the post - secondary section of the national education system, which is made up of universities, polytechnics and colleges of technology including courses as are given by the Colleges of Education, Advanced Teachers Training colleges, correspondence colleges and such institutions as may be allied to them. Tertiary education exercises a direct influence on national productivity, which to a very large extent determines the country's standard of living and help in stimulating local economy as an engine of growth. According to UNESCO (2020), since its foundation, the tertiary education especially university, like any other social institution, has had to confront devastating epidemics that have impacted on their daily operations, and they have survived and pursued their mission even with their doors closed. One of these epidemics that had confronted tertiary education lately is covid-19 pandemic (Isuku and Emunemu;2009; Ogunode, et al., 2020)

Teaching & learning methodologies in tertiary institutions in Post-Covid Period-in Nigeria

The COVID-19 Pandemic has caused the largest disruption of education in history, having already had a near universal impact on learners and teachers around the world, from pre-primary to secondary schools, technical and vocational education and training (TVET) institutions, universities, adult learning, and skills development establishments. By mid-April 2020, 94 per cent of learners worldwide were affected by the pandemic, representing 1.58 billion children and youth, from pre-primary to higher education, in 200 countries. COVID-19 has resulted in schools shut all across the world. Globally, over 1.2 billion

children are out of the classroom. As a result, education has changed dramatically, with the distinctive rise of e-learning, whereby teaching is undertaken remotely and on digital platforms. Research suggests that online learning has been shown to increase retention of information, and take less time, meaning the changes coronavirus have caused might be here to stay. While countries are at different points in their COVID-19 infection rates, worldwide there are currently more than 1.2 billion children in 186 countries were affected by school closures due to the pandemic. (2020 Human Development Perspectives, 2020, New York: UNDP)

The novel Coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic broke out in Wuhan, China in December 2019. In the early days of the crisis, most African countries including Nigeria focused their response on either repatriating or sending assistance to their students who were stranded in Wuhan. This response has changed, as the pandemic has since spread into African countries including Nigeria. On February 27, 2020, Nigeria confirmed and recorded her first case of Covid-19; the index case was an Italian who had just returned to Nigeria from his home country. From the initial cases of imported transmission, Nigeria recorded community-transmission cases. This has resulted in thousands of confirmed cases of covid-19 in the country. In a bid to curtail the spread of the virus, the initial response of the Nigerian Government was the closure of all schools, including universities beginning in March 2020. Consequently, all students ranging from undergraduate to postgraduate students had to leave their university campuses, putting an abrupt end to academic activities and disrupting academic calendars across various institutions. There are one hundred and seventy-four (174) Universities in Nigeria (National Universities Commission,

2020); the mode of teaching has been the traditional method, which consists of lecturers or teachers having physical meetings with students in a classroom building for the purposes of lecture, examinations, seminars and project/thesis defense. Ifijeh et al. (2015) observed that very few Nigerian universities operate e-learning platforms, which merely allowed for upload and download of lecture notes, as well as giving and submission of students' assignment or test (Ifijeh et al. 2015; Kandola, 2020)

Before now, the only resemblance of out-of-campus teaching and learning program was the distance education program run by a few institutions in the country. However, no real online teaching takes place, as students are required to visit the campus periodically and are provided with materials which they take home for further studies. As a result, tertiary institutions and their students especially government owned institutions are finding it difficult to adapt to other means of teaching and learning which would come in place or improvise the normal classroom activities of face-to-face teaching and learning. In respect to the above and in a report prepared by the technical team of the UNESCO International Institute for Higher Education (2020) the traditional distance education mode, where the teacher continues to teach in a regular class setting that is broadcast live and can be retrieved at a later time, seems to be the most appreciated by students because this best reproduces the dynamics to which they are accustomed. (Ifijeh & Yusuf, 2020)

It was a glaring fact that, Nigeria tertiary education has been in shambles ranging from the constant loggerheads between the federal government and tertiary institution unions especially Academic Staff of Nigerian Universities (ASUU), decrease in the budget meant for education and poor

infrastructures. Now that the pandemic has occurred, its effect would worsen the situation of tertiary education in Nigeria. According to Ogunode et al (2020), the after effect of COVID-19 to the tertiary education ranges from disruption of academic calendar, cancelation of already planned local and international conferences, teaching and learning gap, loss of workforce in educational institutions and cut in budget of higher education. Simon and Hans (2020) submitted that the global lockdown of education institutions is going to cause major (and likely unequal) interruption in students' learning; disruptions in internal assessments; and the cancellation of public assessments for qualifications or their replacement by an inferior alternative. Ogunode (2020) observed that the closure of all educational institutions from primary schools to the higher institutions would affect the students' academic plans and programme because many of the higher institutions have started their first semester exams. Furthermore, teaching and learning in most Nigerian tertiary institutions will never follow the normal process because at resumption, most institutions would want to run through their academic calendars thereby putting tensions and pressures on students and teachers to finish the set-out course outline for the year. In the words of Aina and Opeyemi (2020), the educational system of the world was halted because of social distancing and the lockdown, the conventional paradigm of teaching fails and teaching/learning suffers a severe setback all over the world including Nigeria. In the part of budget cut due to covid-19 and its effect on the Nigerian economy, Cseaafrica (2020) submitted that the Nigerian federal budget for the 2020 fiscal year was prepared with significant revenue expectations but with contestable realizations. This would affect the budget for

years to come. (Aina and Opeyemi, 2020; Cseaafrica,2020)

Theoretical framework of the use of hand-held devices

In this modern age of the use of technology for learning, there are theories been postulated and champion the rationale for their usage and such type of those theory is the constructivist learning ideologies which is becoming more recognized because they typically believe that learning should be student-centered, collaborative and active. In this sense, teachers who integrate technology into instruction are likely to hold student-centered constructivist pedagogical beliefs and a stereotype of this new paradigm shift in teaching and learning process with the use of hand held devices for instruction process. Similarly, the constructivist belief that people develop and build understanding from their own personal and subjective experiences. Students go along with prior experience (past experiences) into their academics and use it to improve and better their learning by gaining additional knowledge and build upon their old. though teacher can be excellent and excel at implementing constructivist learning theory in conjunction with digital devices , students may not actually learn. The students need to have the opportunity to experiment and utilize previous experiences to build new understandings of the educational material. Constructivist learning theory allows digital devices to concentrate on the student's ability to be self-directed in learning and draw conclusions. Therefore, theoretical framework on hand-held is akin to some related theories in existence such as digital divide, digital exclusion, digital literacy and digital inclusion which has thrown up certain identifiable thought patterns, explanations and conjectures. These articulations have enjoyed considerable consistency in the body of available literature may be adjudged as appropriate theoretical foundations and

reference point for studies in the use of hand held and digital inclusion. (Karagiorgi & Symeou 2005)

Categories of hand-held devices for instructional uses in reducing crisis in curriculum delivery

Most educational institutions in Nigeria are currently based only on traditional methods of learning including schools, colleges and universities. This means that they follow the traditional set up of face-to-face lectures in a classroom. However, some academic units have introduced the use of technology to facilitate academic activities and revamp old procedures. For instance, the face of educational sector in Nigeria is changing gradually as evident in the obvious progress of the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), a distance learning institution whose course delivery is digitally facilitated through a combination of Web based modules, textual materials, audio and video tapes as well as CD-ROMs. More so, so many universities now have approved Distance Learning Centres (National Universities Commission, 2020) and as well use digital learning tools for their semester exams. In addition, as reported by over five hundred thousand students gain admission into various tertiary institutions in Nigeria each year through computer-based exam of the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB). These and many more are responsible for the gradual exposure of the students, academics and institutions to the digital world. (Ajikoba 2017; Dhawan, 2020)

There are different categorizations or taxonomies of hand-held mobile devices which can be used for instructional purposes to bring about effectiveness in teaching and can go a long way to reduce crisis associated with curriculum delivery However, before discussing such it is important to discuss the

various forms of small devices available because each type of device gives different options for use by students, educators and school administrators. At present, there appear to be a few different broad categories of handhelds along with some sub-categories. One category is the smart phone. The iPhone and the Android phone can be categorized as smart phones. There are several other brands that fit into this category but these two by far make up the bulk of the market and reference currently. A smart phone starts with the phone concept and adds in the ability to run other applications (normally called just “apps”) such as web browsers and a host of other types of programs. Another category would be those devices that are similar to smart phones but do not have the capability to make or receive phone calls. In this category would be devices such as the iPad™, the iPod Touch™ and a host of other similar devices. This category is in the process of being refined into two different groups. The first, and more traditional group, is the pocket-sized MP3 player. The smallest of these can simply play music while the larger, more sophisticated ones, can do almost everything a smart phone can do except handle phone calls. The second group is a bit larger and more powerful. This group includes devices such as the Amazon Kindle, the Barnes and Noble Nook and, of course the iPad which sparked a revolution in thinking about the personal computer and small devices. (Anderson, 2010; Shehu, 2015).

In the perspective of Walsh (2012), On handheld mobile technologies he submitted that there are nine most ranking technologies called the top nine emerging education and instructional technologies and resources which are:

1. The flipped classroom: It is a spring pose in form of the rhetorical question and intuition for distribution awareness

concerning the influential idea of presentation which continues to grow.

2. The apple iPad and other tablet devices: The iPad has proliferated at a rate far surpassing any other technology introduction. This is because they have high level of connectivity with WIFI and GPRS.
3. Smart phones: We cannot continue to ignore these ubiquitous devices. The vast majority of students in high schools and colleges have them. They are great for interactive polling, tweeting and research purpose.
4. Gamification of education: There are many reasons why this idea is gaining popularity including that it can deliver. The Khan Academy is using it, is leveraging gamification (and many of the other ideas).
5. Emergence of free online courses: The MOOCs (massive open online courses) are just one option for learning – massive open online courses are not all free courses and vice-versa.
6. 1 to 1 and BYOD (Bring your own device) initiatives: Many educators feel passionately that ‘1 to 1’ makes a lot of sense it’s an ideal that can be so engaging and that overlaps with some of the other tools and techniques.
7. Cloud apps for file storage, note-taking, and more: Internet tools are relevant apps in instruction for a quiet numbers of years. Other cloud apps are seeing explosive growth, encouraged by the increasing tendency for computer users to have multiple devices from which they want to access their own personal content.
8. OER (Open Educational Resources): Is a transformational idea that can play an important role in changing the nature, availability, and costs of educational materials, content, and tools.

9. **Learning Analytics:** Is another technology that has really begun to gain momentum over the years or so, and is clearly focused on enhancing learning outcomes by leveraging data. After seeing the phrase pop up repeatedly in educational technology media, a month later delved into Learning Analytics and may only be emerging from its infancy, but the growing number of institutions and organizations working to deliver and leverage the concept positions it as one of the top technologies that can help to deliver on the promise of increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of instruction through the thoughtful and informed application of information technologies (Walsh 2012).

While According to Anderson (2010). Identified the following categories of Handheld-mobile devices and there instructional used at post-covid in tertiary institutions of learning in Nigeria as thus:

Smart Phone:

Smart phone has an integrated functionality in it. Such functions include inbuilt camera, networking and internet access, mass storage, telephone and video functions in one compact system. There are different usages of this mobile technology amongst are: Teachers and students can use it to play video, audio and flash movies. Moreso, it can be use for audio and video lectures download and as well edit online text. Used for sending IM and text messages and use the phone for mass storage. Smart phone also enable global collaboration and scientific experimentation and research. Users also can access information globally. Smart phones thus support interactive learning. There are different type of mobile phones depend on their sophistication. (Anderson, 2010; Shehu,2015).

Personal Digital Assistant:

Personal digital assistant, PDA has different forms of functionality because of its inherent or in build features, such as access to internet, computing ability and networking characteristics. It is well design mobile technology that equally has note pad; book address; calendar and other important productivity functions

Instructional uses: PDA play audio, video, and Flash movies; displays and permits editing of text documents; allows the users to check email , used as mass storage and SMS & IM text messages. PDAs support interactive, collaborative learning. Students can use them to present projects; conduct research; word process documents (with a peripheral input device); and take notes in class . (Anderson, 2010; Shehu,2015).

The Personal Media Player (PMP) or Personal Media Centre (PMC)

This is a relatively new class of mobile device. These systems are focused on media delivery and can play, store and manage a variety of digital media formats. A fundamental classification within these three types of devices is between those that are able to connect to the Internet and those that cannot. Livingston (2004) coins the term MIAD: Mobile Internet Access Device. The emergence of technologies such as Wi-Fi (802.11) and 3G which permit such high level of connectivity have opened up a new arena of prospective for mobile technologies (Anderson, 2010; Shehu,2015).

Ultra-Mobile PC (UMPC):

An ultra mobile PCs have the characteristics of a standard tablet personal computer, but it is relatively small in term of package. They support audio, video, and surfing the internet; and other communication and networking applications. They have inbuilt Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, and Ethernet enable.

Instructional uses: Students can download audio and video lectures and

podcasts to their UMPCs; create and edit course-related assignment; surf the web; send e-mail, and other important functions such as sending IMs, and text-messages. UMPCs enable global collaboration, scientific experimentation, and research. Users also can access information globally. UMPCs thus enable interactive learning. (Anderson, 2010).

iPod: The iPod portable media player allows users to download music, audio books, podcasts, photos, and video. It has an address books and calendar that synchronize with Microsoft's Outlook or Outlook Express. iPod has several instructional uses. With the iPod; students can download podcast of relevant instructional materials along with audio and video lectures. The video ipod, for example, allows students to exchange information files, collaborate on projects work and prepare for exams, showcase their work, and share project results. The instructor has the advantage of providing stage-by-stage explanation that is not possible with words. Additionally, learners or the teachers can attach microphone to the iPods in order to capture material for educational use. (Anderson, 2010).

Importance of the use of hand-held mobile devices for curriculum delivery @ tertiary institutions

The 21st Century students across the globe are digital natives and most of them were being exposed to one form of handheld digital mobile devices or the other. Some could have used them for business while others could be for education or entertainment. But more specifically, at tertiary level its importance can include the following:

1. Allow for individualized instructional process because the learner interacted with the device to carry out instructional strategy at his/her pace within a given topic

2. It reduces learning poverty in our tertiary institution of learning
3. It transforms teaching and learning to digital thereby breaking the monopoly of traditional physical face to face interaction between the teacher and the learners all the time
4. IT provides opportunity and allow for collaborative learning among the students
5. flexibility, efficiency in knowledge and qualification enhancement, motivation of students' interaction, cost-effective, and others.
6. Enhanced learning: research shows increased depth of understanding and retention of course content; more meaningful discussions; emphasis on writing skills, technology skills, and life skills like time management, independence, and self-discipline.
7. Leveling of the playing field: students can take more time to think and reflect before communicating; shy students tend to thrive online; anonymity is guaranteed in an online environment.
8. Interaction: increased student-to-teacher and student-to-student interaction and discussion; a more student-centered learning environment; less passive listening and more active learning; a greater sense of connectedness, synergy.
9. Innovative teaching: student-centered approaches; increased variety and creativity of learning activities; address different learning styles; changes and improvements can translate to on-ground courses as well
10. Improved administration: time to examine student work more thoroughly; ability to document and record online interactions; ability to manage grading online.
11. Savings: accommodate more students; increased student satisfaction, higher retention and fewer repeats.

12. Maximize physical resources: lessen demand on limited campus infrastructure; decrease congestion on campus and parking lots. (Pande, Wadhai, and Thakare 2016).

Impediments associated with the use of hand-held devices in tertiary Institutions- In Nigeria

Small electronic devices, also referred to as handhelds, are impacting education in a variety of ways including teaching methods, student life, and the need for support from technical staff. This chapter discusses the importance of handhelds in education, how handhelds are being used in education, the challenges presented by handhelds for those in education and what might happen with handhelds in the future. These portable handheld electronic devices such as computer tablets and smartphones continue to offer amazing features incorporated from mass-produced electronic technology. Sometimes, these commercial off the shelf (COTS) devices do not quite meet user needs. Perhaps they do not withstand tough environmental conditions, require a custom interface, or don't meet regulatory requirements driven by specific application use cases. A custom designed handheld device may be necessary for these situations.

Specific challenges associated with the use of handheld devices for learning can include but limited to the following:

1. It is a challenge to design and produce cost-effective custom handheld devices that meet operational needs and specification
2. Weakness of internet connection and internet speed in many of our universities
3. High prices for a good internet connectivity
4. Absence of customized computers/laptops/tablets/smartphones

that support online teaching and learning

5. Many online instruments, platforms, and websites crashed when an unexpectedly high number of clients connected to them.
6. Unethical behavior, physical health concerns, and data privacy issues.
7. Cheating via text messaging, and sharing inappropriate content, and possibly Cell phones provide an additional means for cyberbullying.
8. There has been wide diversity among the mobile devices themselves in terms of available features and proprietary platforms, and designs are not always optimal for all learners owing to limited capabilities for text entry,
9. small screen sizes, and limited battery life.

Conclusion

Covid-19 has eaten deep into the education sector particularly tertiary education in Nigeria. Its emergence has caused major issues ranging from hunger associated with partial or total lockdown, limited freedom of movement and association, and psychological trauma caused by fear of contracting this dreaded contagious disease. In the aspect of teaching and learning, Covid19 has affected the traditional classroom activities of face-to-face teaching and learning involving lecturers and students in tertiary institutions. It has forced the adoption of online teaching and learning which is not presently practiced in Nigerian tertiary institutions especially government owned institutions at the moment because of the lack of necessary infrastructures needed to embark on fully fledged online teaching and learning, couple with frequent industrial action embarked by the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU), has worsen instructional process delivery in our tertiary

institutions, in Nigeria. However, with the full adoptions and uses of hand-held mobile devices for instructional process, backlog and uncovered contents in various disciplines can be bridge within possible shortest period of time

Recommendations

1. The federal and State governments must as a matter of urgent necessary action enforce the UNESCO recommendation of 20% to 26% budgetary allocation to education in Nigeria. In order to put in place the needed infrastructure and facilities to facilitates full adoption and utilization of handheld device
2. Concise efforts must be initiated inform of policy towards the liberalization of the educational sector from the bureaucratic bottle neck that has bedeviled its transformational development over the years by institutionalizing transparency and accountability in the system.
3. The National Communication commission (NCC) should work hard through the Network providers to ensure at least 70% internet penetration in Nigeria and Nigeria public universities
4. The federal government through the National Universities commission (NUC) liberalize the educational sector to accommodate full fledged digital learning.in our tertiary institute

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